

Fostering Energy Justice through Decentralised Transition: The Case of Energy Communities in Greece

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Abstract

This paper explores the potential of Energy Communities (ECs) as a conduit for achieving energy justice and a just transition in Greece's energy sector and promote socio-economic development. It provides an overview of the relevant framework of climate governance strategies, positioning the role of ECs in these. The paper presents a comprehensive country-level survey ($n > 1000$) investigating Greek households' perceptions of energy justice, their awareness of and attitudes towards ECs, and their willingness to participate in or invest in ECs. The findings highlight the challenges and opportunities of ECs in Greece's energy transition and suggest the need for increased public awareness, equitable energy policies, and inclusive decision-making processes. In the context of the ongoing energy transition in Greece, the article argues that energy communities although possessing a valuable agency and mobilise a widely accepted discourse that can contribute to a just transition promoting social and environmental justice, require further institutional enablers in order to challenge the structure of the current socio-economic status quo.

Keywords

Energy communities,
Just transition,
Energy justice,
Greece, Citizens'
engagement

Introduction

Given the urgency of the climate crisis, there is an increasing demand for transformative change and innovation within the energy system. Governments are facing the pressing task of swiftly reducing greenhouse gases emissions in a system that is growing in complexity, which inherently poses risks (Hampton et al., 2021). In Europe, since the early 2000s, the European Union (EU) has consistently followed a relatively progressive path in climate governance, with a notable increase in ambition and a broader range of policies. Significant progress has also been made in integrating climate policies into other areas. This upward growth trajectory was marked by the introduction of the European Green Deal (EGD) (Fetting, 2019) in late 2019, a package of policy initiatives, that aims to set the EU on the path to climate neutrality by 2050 (Von Homeyer et al., 2021). The energy sector is one of the major sources of greenhouse gas emissions globally, through the burning of fossil fuels for electricity generation, transportation, heating, and major industrial processes. As a result, the decarbonisation of the

sector and its transition to a renewable energy- based system is essential to address climate change effectively. Consequently, a lot of policy attention is directed to the sector while the implications of the Russia-Ukraine war in the energy security of Europe further strengthened EU's commitment to the phase-out of fossil fuels and accelerated the clean energy transition, as new, targets that are more ambitious and strategies set via the REPowerEU plan¹.

One of the main non-technological challenges of the clean energy transition is to achieve it in a socially equitable manner. The debate surrounding "just transition" involves addressing social and economic inequalities, promoting fairness and inclusivity, and ensuring that vulnerable communities, workers, and regions aren't disproportionately impacted by the transition. The concept originates from the labour movement and concerns the fair treatment of workers and communities as economies shift towards more sustainable practices, including the energy sector. This concept has evolved to include broader considerations of social justice, particularly in relation to climate change mitigation efforts (Newell and Mulvaney, 2013; Heffron and McCauley, 2018).

Just-transition goals to address the challenges of energy insecurity, energy poverty, and climate change necessitates the mobilisation of new financial resources, the development of innovative technologies, and significant reforms to institutions and policy-making processes, are rather important for economic development, social equity and environmental protection (UN, 2015). Institutional top-down target-setting work on this domain had been framed as access to sustainable and affordable energy became part of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals and the EU's European Pillar of Social Rights. Along the emergence of initiatives, policies and new regulatory frameworks aiming to the energy transition were standing out, like the *clean energy for all Europeans* package, which was approved in 2019, aiming to the decarbonization of the European Union's energy system, aligning with the objectives of the EGD.

In parallel, the EU's long-standing cohesion policy via its strong territorial dimension promotes integrated territorial and local development strategies, in order to address the diverse development needs across Europe's cities and regions while helping the less developed European countries and regions to catch up (Pertoldi et al., 2022). The goal of a balanced and inclusive participation of countries, regions, businesses and individuals is also shared in the energy policy domain and largely expressed via the just transition narrative. In the framework of a just energy transition to a sustainable and low-carbon future, balanced territorial development is essential. It incorporates the notion of comprehensive and integrated energy and development strategies that take into account the special qualities, assets, and requirements of a particular region or territory. This underscores the crucial role of localised

¹ European Commission, Communication REPowerEU Plan: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2022%3A230%3AFIN> 2022.

initiatives in fostering fairness and inclusivity in the transition towards sustainable energy practices.

Integrating Energy Communities (ECs) into the energy transition and territorial development strategies may be a key tool of effective policy making in both areas. Indeed, since the 2000s, many countries, as the Netherlands, Germany and the UK, had put together ambitious visions about how to become ‘energy neutral’, ‘zero-emission’ or ‘low carbon’ (Van der Schoor, 2016), and aimed to stimulate local energy production capacity on an individual as well as a cooperative basis.

The mentioned “Clean Energy for All Europeans” EU policy package formally acknowledges ECs as a new participant within the European energy system. Furthermore, it recognizes the crucial role that ECs can potentially fulfil, as they embody principles of equity and inclusivity in line with just-transition goals. Indeed, ECs may assume a transformative role in territorial development and the pursuit of a just transition. These communities can empower local actors by actively involving them in the generation, distribution, and consumption of renewable energy through decentralised and community-driven projects. By championing localised energy production and democratic decision-making, ECs generate economic diversification, job opportunities, and the retention of economic benefits within the region. Moreover, their emphasis on community ownership and participation fosters social cohesion and inclusivity.

By stimulating the growth of community energy projects, a multitude of benefits for energy consumers that align with the principles of energy justice is anticipated. The concept of ECs revolves around facilitating collaborative energy initiatives that emphasise open, democratic participation, and governance. The overarching goal is to deliver benefits and enhance resilience for the members of local communities (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020). EC initiatives adopt diverse legal structures. While some initiatives may not necessitate a specific legal form, community ownership often requires the creation of a legal entity capable of entering agreements, assuming responsibilities, and conducting activities on behalf of its members. Throughout Europe, a wide range of legal forms has been utilised, including cooperatives, partnerships, community interest companies, foundations, non-profit organisations, various types of social enterprises, and associations (Roberts, 2020).

Given the above framework, this paper aims to fill a knowledge gap regarding just transition trajectories in Southern Europe. We present and analyse public perception survey data to provide a comprehensive picture of the current state of energy justice and energy communities in Greece, contributing to the broader conversation on how to achieve a more equitable and sustainable energy future. A significant novelty in comparison to most studies examining the links of just transition and ECs regards the fact that in those usually the object of analysis is existing ECs themselves and their stakeholders (Bommel & Höffken, 2021; Lupi et al., 2021; Hanke & Guyet, 2023). Our analysis focuses on broader public opinions of non-

energy community stakeholders, and includes awareness and knowledge of ECs, attitudes towards ECs, demographic and socio-economic data, perceptions of energy justice, and barriers to participation. The paper's insights serve as valuable inputs in aligning development strategies with the principles of energy justice, fostering a holistic approach to sustainable and inclusive energy practices at the local level.

Energy Justice and Energy Communities

Energy justice plays a significant role in a just transition by addressing fairness and equity issues within the existing energy system that is often extractive in nature. The concept has emerged as a framework that integrates concerns about the social and ethical aspects of energy production, distribution, and consumption. It is closely linked to the principles of deep democracy, cooperation, and regeneration, which are all key components of the just transition framework, while can serve as an analytical conceptual, analytical, and decision-making tool (Sovacool and Dworkin, 2015). Indeed today, energy justice has become a pressing issue, with experts advocating for actions to avoid perpetuating or creating new inequalities during the energy transition (Heffron 2022; Jenkins et al., 2020). Rather than solely focusing on implementing new technologies, developing a new energy system should prioritise creating a fair and equitable distribution of both the benefits and burdens of energy services and encourage inclusive decision-making (Sovacool et al., 2017).

The literature on energy justice often centres around three key principles: distributional, procedural, and recognitional, which have been discussed in various studies (Jenkins et al., 2016; Sovacool and Dworkin, 2015). This represents an expansion of the broader environmental justice debates, describing recognition, participation and capability as key justice components, in the energy field (Schlosberg, 2007). According to Goldthau and Sovacool (2012), distributive justice is concerned with ensuring that the entire population has access to and shares in the advantages of the energy industry. In order for each stakeholder to participate fairly in the decision-making of energy infrastructures, procedural justice focuses on the legal side of energy justice (Thomas et al., 2020). The importance of both formal and substantive equality is emphasised by recognitional justice (Pellegrini-Masini et al., 2020). By emphasising on the diversity of all people and the need to engage them in the energy transition, recognition is a strategy to address distributional and procedural fairness (Heffron and McCauley, 2017; Walker and Day, 2012).

The current discourse in energy community literature revolves around the inquiry into whether ECs facilitate a fair, democratic, and just transition in the energy landscape. ECs. has been perceived as a potentially perfect embodiment of energy citizenship and energy democracy (Strachan et al., 2015), and already address pressing social issues like energy poverty (Koukoufikis et al., 2023) though their actual social and environmental effects can vary (Berka and Creamer, 2018).

The energy justice framework is progressively utilised to examine diverse community energy processes and outcomes, exploring their capacity to promote energy justice (Mudaca et al., 2018; van Bommel & Höffken, 2021; Dudka et al., 2023). This comes as no surprise since ECs could be seen as a solution to the need for a balanced approach that integrates security, poverty, and climate change within energy policy frameworks ensuring that energy transitions do not exacerbate existing social inequalities (McCauley et al., 2019). How ECs can promote energy justice is especially evident when discussing democratic participation and the potential to enable citizens to actively participate in the energy transition, echoing Schlosberg's (2007) emphasis on participation and capability (Becker & Naumann, 2017).

Current policy initiatives in Europe encourage the development of community energy projects, with the explicit goal of facilitating a fair transition to a low-carbon energy system (Mengolini & Masera, 2021). This is since legislative and non-legislative policies can diffuse local community initiatives in the energy sector as they are mutually influenced and propelled by advancements in the field (Matschoss et al., 2022).

Nevertheless, while ECs tackle energy matters locally, the attainment of energy justice must extend to a systemic level. To achieve this, bold political measures are necessary to address issues at their roots (Meynen & Marin, 2022). It is crucial to emphasise that the responsibility for addressing energy-related vulnerabilities remains with the welfare state, and there should be no transfer of this responsibility from social policy to local communities (Hanke & Guyet, 2023).

In our paper, we will assess the ECs potential to promote energy justice in Greece focusing mainly on the procedural and distributive pillars of the concept of energy justice, and in particular on issues of accessibility, equity, participation and governance.

Accessibility ensures that everyone, regardless of socioeconomic status or geographic location, has access to affordable, reliable, and sustainable energy (IEA, 2020). This includes issues such as energy poverty, energy access in rural or remote areas, ensuring for example that vulnerable communities have access to the benefits of renewable energy technologies.

Equity addresses the unequal distribution of energy resources and ensures that everyone benefits from the energy transition (Sovacool and Dworkin, 2015). It includes issues such as fair allocation of costs and benefits, energy affordability for low-income households, and access to clean energy for marginalised communities.

Participation requires that communities and stakeholders have a say in energy decision-making and policy development (Jenkins, 2019). It includes issues such as community engagement, democratic decision-making processes, and access to information or resources to participate effectively.

Finally, governance refers to the promotion of a just and democratic energy system through effective governance structures and policies (Sovacool et al, 2016b). It includes issues

such as transparent and fair regulation, accountability of energy producers, and policies that prioritise the social, economic, and environmental dimensions of energy.

Energy communities with their democratic decision making processes, the equity on benefits sharing, the structures that support inclusivity and capacity building can address energy justice issues. However, it is important to note that achieving energy justice requires a broader and more comprehensive approach than just creating ECs. Other factors such as government policies, socioeconomic disparities, and energy infrastructure also play a significant role in achieving energy justice. Additionally, there may be potential barriers to the implementation of ECs in Greece, such as legal frameworks, funding, and technical challenges, which should be closely examined and addressed in order to ensure that ECs can contribute to achieving energy justice in the country.

Methodology

In the pursuit of a sustainable and equitable energy future, energy justice principles have become a guiding framework, addressing fairness, inclusivity, and environmental integrity in the transition to cleaner energy sources. For an adequate account of territorial socio-economic development, one must refer to the *actions* that steer or interfere with the development processes, the *structures* that both constrain and enable action, the *institutions* that guide or hamper action and mediate the relation between structures and action, and the *discourses* and discursive practices that are part of these interactions (Moulaert, et al., 2016).

Thus in order to combine the socio-spatial and justice elements and conduct our study on ECs and their potential role in facilitating a just energy transition in Greece we adopted a comprehensive approach to data collection. In ensuring the validity of our data in terms of spatial distribution, it's essential to note that our survey respondents were strategically sampled across various regions in Greece. A professional agency specialising in public opinion surveys was engaged to distribute the questionnaire and collect the data. This sampling approach is designed to reflect the population distribution of each region, thereby ensuring representation from diverse geographic areas. By including participants from all over the country, our data provide an encompassing perspective on energy-related viewpoints and experiences, taking into consideration regional differences and dynamics. This regional stratification in the sampling improves the relevance of our results and offers a strong basis for examining energy justice and community involvement across the divergent regions of Greece. Through this study, we are trying to capture and assess the current state of the different elements of energy justice in Greece and explore the potential of ECs within the Greek context.

We initiated our research by conducting a systematic review and analysis of pertinent legislative documents. This encompassed an examination of energy laws such as N4414/2016, N4513/2018, and N5037/2023, in addition to related regulations, policy documents, and

reports. These documents provided us with the foundational legal and policy context essential for our study.

Then, through a thoughtfully designed survey, our primary objective is to identify how these various principles of energy justice resonate with the Greek households. By analysing survey responses, we aim to uncover not only how awareness, attitudes, demographics, perceptions, and barriers intersect with these justice principles but also the extent to which these principles are pertinent in Greece today. This investigation will provide valuable insights into the Greek perspective on energy justice and its relevance in shaping the country's sustainable and just energy landscape. Our research aims to present the Greek reality of energy justice principles and the possible role of ECs, while acknowledging that they are mutually reinforcing and interrelated. To obtain the essential data, the survey was meticulously designed to gather opinions on the various organisational, operational, and economic matters related to energy transition, energy justice and ECs. To ensure widespread participation, we distributed the survey online, collaborating with a non-governmental organisation for its execution.

The survey's questionnaire had the following structure:

1. *Perceptions:*

- Environment: Explore participants' perspectives on the current environmental conditions and concerns.
- Climate Crisis: Assess the level of awareness and concerns regarding the ongoing climate crisis.
- Energy Transition Policies: Gauge opinions on existing energy transition policies and their effectiveness.

2. *Household's Energy Aspects:*

- Energy Cost: Examine participants' experiences and opinions on the cost of energy for their households.
- Energy Prices: Evaluate perceptions of energy prices and their impact on daily life.
- Views on Energy Policies: Understand participants' views on broader energy policies affecting households.

3. *Energy Communities:*

- Knowledge Level: Measure the understanding of participants about the concept and functioning of energy communities.
- Willingness to Participate: Explore participants' openness and interest in actively engaging with energy communities.

4. *Demographics:*

- Gather demographic information to understand the diverse backgrounds and contexts of the participants.

By employing this survey, we aimed to build a coherent understanding of the potential of ECs in Greece within the context of energy justice and the pursuit of just energy transition objectives while using a methodological framework that considers the intricacies of the Greek social and energy landscape, recognizing its unique challenges and opportunities. In our analysis, we will be presenting descriptive statistics to provide a clear and comprehensive overview of the data we have collected. The use of descriptive statistics allows us to summarise and present key features of the dataset, providing insights into central tendencies, variability, and distribution. By presenting these, we strive to extract complex information into manageable, interpretable summaries that enhance the accessibility and clarity of our findings. Finally, we performed a parametric analysis to explore the monetary willingness to invest in these initiatives by greek households.

The ongoing framework of Energy Communities in Greece

In the realm of energy justice, legislation plays a pivotal role in translating principles of fairness, equity, and inclusivity into tangible, legal frameworks that guide the energy sector (ILO, 2015). The European Commission has introduced a comprehensive supportive policy for community energy initiatives across its member states, providing an enabling framework. Nonetheless, as suggested by Hanke and Lowitzsch (2020), the effective realisation of inclusion objectives depend on the adaptation of this framework to the unique life circumstances and behavioural traits of vulnerable consumers when it is transposed into national law. Failing this adaptation, the goal of inclusion is likely to remain unattainable. Consequently, the challenge lies in the national and local implementation and operationalization of this enabling framework (Hanke & Lowitzsch, 2020). In this context, it seems rather important to explore the ongoing framework of energy related legislation in Greece.

In 2016, Greece implemented legislation concerning virtual net metering (law N4414/2016), targeting farmers and municipalities. This move marked the initial advancement towards collective energy sharing. Under this law, charges for public service obligations on net-metering and virtual net-metering installations are determined based on the total energy consumption, which includes the sum of energy withdrawn from the network and consumption from behind the metre. However, network charges, renewable energy tariffs, and other regulated fees are applied solely to the energy physically withdrawn from the public network, excluding consumption behind the metre and energy netting.

In 2018, a significant step was taken in the energy sector with the introduction of law N4513/2018, which focused on ECs and further expanded the scope of virtual net metering to include community energy initiatives. The law defines ECs as urban partnerships driven by the goals of social and solidarity economy, as well as fostering innovation in the energy sector.

According to the first legislation, the primary objectives of ECs are to combat energy poverty, promote energy sustainability, and encourage various aspects such as energy production, energy storage, collective self-consumption, distribution, and supply. Additionally, it is aimed to enhance self-sufficiency and energy security, particularly in island municipalities. ECs are also tasked with supporting efficiency measures at the local and regional levels, promoting cogeneration, rational energy use, energy efficiency, sustainable transportation, and demand-side management. Under the provisions of the law, members of the EC, whether they are natural persons or legal entities, are entitled to participate in virtual net metering. Moreover, vulnerable consumers or citizens living below the poverty line can also be included in the virtual net metering arrangements, provided that the EC consents to their involvement. It is important to note that these individuals don't necessarily need to be members of the Energy Community itself, but they must reside within the same district where the EC is established. By ensuring that energy projects cater to local needs and harness locally available renewable resources, it sought to empower communities and promote collective self-sufficiency, thereby aligning with the distributive and procedural justice principles of energy justice.

The Greek energy community law was setting itself apart from other concepts by tackling distinct concerns like ensuring independent energy supply for islands and combating energy poverty. Moreover, it was deviating from the traditional classification of Renewable Energy Communities (RECs) and Citizen Energy Communities (CECs) based on proximity. Instead, the law was differentiating them based on whether they operate for profit or non-profit purposes (Frieden et al., 2020).

Thus, in March 2023, Greece tried to incorporate all the European Directives as well as the differentiation of RECs and CECs in the law N5037/2023. In both cases, citizens, businesses, and local communities have the opportunity to take part, with the distinction being that farmers' associations are exclusively eligible for participation in RECs.

However, the introduction of the new law raised great concerns among Greek ECs and other relevant national and European support institutions, which addressed an extensive letter² listing every problematic provision of the new law to the minister of Energy. The greatest concern refers to the transitional period introduced by the new law, which is expected to cause further uncertainty in the existing ecosystem of ECs in Greece operating under the legal framework of the previous law (N4513/2018).

A pivotal aspect of law 4513/2018 revolves around the concept of locality, emphasising the creation of collaborations within energy projects that cater to local requirements and leverage locally available renewable energy resources, ultimately ensuring that the community's members reap the rewards. It imposes a requirement that more than half (50%

² Available in Greek: <https://www.greenpeace.org/static/planet4-greece-stateless/2023/03/bf11a6df-greenpeace-greece-sxoliasmos-desmis-energeiakon-koinotiton-pros-ypen-20230308.pdf>

+1) of an energy community's members have a connection to the geographical area where the project is officially registered. This requirement is no longer valid according to the new law.

In addition, it expressed the concern regarding the article that allows the establishment of ECs exclusively by enterprises. This provision of the new law contradicts the Article 2(11) of Directive 2019/944³, which distinctively refers to the open and voluntary participation of citizens in ECs, as well as to citizen control over them.

Another significant alteration is that a minimum of 30 members is now necessary to establish a community, a notable increase from the previous requirement of five. This change aims to prevent the misuse of the framework by individuals who have no genuine intention of setting up a power plant but rather seek to exploit the system by selling their producer licence. However, several concerns have been expressed related to the ability of 30 individuals to get together and establish an EC from scratch.

Finally, it is worth noting that the new legislation currently lacks provisions addressing several critical aspects of transitioning an EC established under the 2018 law to one of the new legal structures. There is no provision regarding the Final Connection Offers, the Connection Contracts and the general procedures for the licensing and construction of the ongoing community energy projects. Specifically, while the 2018 law permits the involvement of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in virtual net-metering projects, the 2023 law excludes them. However, it does not specify how existing Connection Contracts would be impacted in the event of a change in the EC's legal structure. The absence of guidance in the new legislation can leave ECs grappling with how to adapt their existing operations to comply with the new legal requirements, potentially disrupting their ongoing activities. At the same time, this uncertain environment may discourage prospective investors and collaborators from participating in ECs, impeding the expansion of sustainable energy initiatives.

In conclusion, the lack of provisions addressing the transition of ECs from the 2018 law to the 2023 law introduces a high degree of uncertainty across multiple dimensions, including legal, operational, financial, and investor confidence. Addressing these uncertainties and providing clear guidance for the transition is essential for ensuring the smooth evolution of ECs and the continued growth of renewable energy projects in Greece.

Energy Communities status and challenges

Data over the number, status and maturity of ECs in Greece are scarce and not centrally available since the digital register of "*Renewable Energy Communities and Citizen Energy Communities*" is not yet operational. A first mapping effort of ECs in Greece in 2020 took place 2.5 years into the new legislative framework where 409 energy communities had been identified according to the country's General Commercial Registry (GEMI) (Electra, 2020). By November 2022, their number rose to 1,406 according to another mapping study using the

³ Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32019L0944>

same data source accounting for 14% of the total installed capacity of RES projects in the country (The GreenTank, 2023). This can be considered a general success over the acceptance of the ECs as a new institution however further analysis indicates that the operationalisation of those projects is yet not adequate. The number of cancelled projects ranges between 10% and 30% approximately (depending on the type of electrification requests and region) while limited grid availability leads to rejections for the project's interconnection (The GreenTank, 2023). Indeed, the lack of grid availability for energy community virtual net-metering projects is a major issue as almost half of the requests (49%) for projects in the low-medium voltage were rejected by the Hellenic Electricity Distribution Network Operator (HEDNO) over the period November 2021 - November 2022 (The GreenTank, 2023). As a result, less than 17% of the requested capacity had been electrified (ibid).

Figure 1 - Energy communities in Greece (August 2020) and regional population Source: Authors, based on Electra, 2020 data and eurostat

The installed capacity of virtual net-metering RES projects by ECs is much lower than that of RES projects by the for-profit ECs, indicating that ECs are mainly used by individuals and SMSs as instruments in order to profit from the sale of electricity rather than to meet their own energy needs (The GreenTank, 2023). Indeed, there is a wide speculation that

entrepreneurs had used the legal entity of ECs as a vehicle to advance private for profit RES projects utilising legal gaps. The vast majority of projects are reporting a low initial invested cooperative capital less than 10,000 euro (Electra, 2020) which can be attributed to multiple factors from financial constraints and risk aversion to a private investment masquerading as an energy community.

Finally, when it comes to territorial analysis a spatial segregation across the country is observed in regards to the density of the initiatives. The vast majority of them are established in the north part of the country (regions of central, western and east Macedonia) while in the south mainland and islands regions there are a limited number of initiatives (Electra, 2020; The GreenTank, 2023).

Public perceptions on energy justice

Up to our knowledge this survey is the first of its kind in Greece, and delves into public attitudes, beliefs, and behaviours regarding the energy transition, uncovering knowledge gaps and misconceptions about ECs and the overall energy scheme. Conducted from February 3rd to February 15th, 2022, it engaged 1,241 households representing 3,167 citizens, offering a window into the populace's diverse demographics.

Demographics

Gender representation among survey participants included 41.9% women, 57.4% men, and 0.4% non-binary individuals. Age distribution was broad, with 20% aged 18-35, 43% between 35-50, and 37% over 50. Educationally, the sample was varied: 0.2% had only primary education, 2.19% finished lower secondary, 22% upper secondary, nearly 40% had a university degree, and 22.2% held postgraduate qualifications, including Master's or Ph.D. degrees.

A notable 48% of the sampled population spends over 10% of their household income on energy, indicating potential energy poverty—a condition where a significant portion of income goes toward energy, impacting the ability to afford other essentials (Halkos, G., & Kostakis, 2023). This data is crucial for informing policy that resonates with public experience and values, shaping interventions that directly address the realities of energy expenditure and its implications on household welfare.

Figure 2 - Survey's sample demographics

Perceptions on energy transition

In the societal context of energy justice, our survey uncovers compelling insights into public opinion on the political significance of addressing various environmental issues. Public acceptance, as Roddis et al. (2018) emphasise, is essential for energy justice and the successful energy transition. This is particularly pertinent for renewable energy projects, which face challenges in public engagement and participatory decision-making, mirroring the wider issues in the industrial sector. These challenges, often linked to distributive and procedural injustices (Levenda et al., 2021), highlight the need for inclusive and fair processes in energy developments.

Respondents prioritise these concerns differently, with 59.8% advocating for high political priority on the energy transition and renewable energy sources (RES). Addressing the climate crisis is a high priority for 63% of participants, while a striking 78.8% view environmental pollution and its health impacts as urgent political issues. Additionally, 68.4% believe that extreme weather events should be a key political focus. These figures collectively signal an overwhelming demand for greater political commitment to environmental challenges, particularly in the realms of renewable energy, climate change, pollution, and weather-related disasters. In terms of attitudes toward RES, the data reveals that a vast majority, 73%, hold positive or very positive views. Only a small fraction, 8.6%, view RES negatively, and about

one-fourth of respondents are neutral. This sentiment reflects a general optimism about renewable energy among the population surveyed.

Figure 3 - Citizen's viewpoints on political importance over environmental affairs

Figure 4 - Citizen's viewpoints on renewable energy sources

When it comes to the role of transitioning from fossil fuels to renewables in combating the climate crisis, 35.2% of respondents predict a highly positive impact, and 28.2% expect a moderately positive one. A smaller group, 17%, remains cautious about the potential benefits, and only 8.1% see no impact. Overall, these views underscore a prevalent optimism regarding the role of renewable energy in mitigating climate change.

Perceptions on accessibility and equity

The findings from this survey shed light on a pressing issue related to energy justice in Greece – energy poverty; also an issue of accessibility. A significant 78.3% of participants acknowledged energy poverty as a notable concern, with 42.3% identified it as a significant

issue. Given that Greece records one of the highest energy poverty rates in the EU (Koukoufikis & Uihlein, 2022), these findings indicate the widespread challenges households face in affording energy bills and achieving comfortable living standards, highlighting the urgency for targeted social and economic interventions. A considerable segment of the population is financially burdened by energy costs, with implications for their well-being and life quality. Ensuring equitable access to affordable and sustainable energy is paramount for both individual welfare and societal benefit.

Figure 5 - Citizen's perception over the intensity of energy poverty

In the literature, the proportion of income allocated to energy bills, is a commonly used objective measure of energy poverty (Churchill et al, 2020). Thus, taking a closer look at how the percentage of income spent for energy bills in combination with the income clusters of responders, can provide useful insights regarding the distribution of energy-related economic burdens.

Our analysis reveals disparities in energy expenses relative to income, with lower-income households shouldering a disproportionate energy burden. Specifically, 14.16% of households earning under €7,000 and 24.5% of those in the €10,000 - €15,000 bracket spend more than 10% of their income on energy. In contrast, higher-income households (earning €20,000 - €30,000 and above) generally allocate up to 5% of their income to energy, indicating more financial flexibility. This uneven financial commitment across income levels suggests distributive injustice in the energy sector.

The discussion also underscores the multifaceted nature of energy poverty, energy services like heating, lighting, and space cooling, becoming elusive for energy-poor households, leading to a disproportionately high share of energy expenditure in their total income—defined as the 'energy burden.' Notably, the lowest-income households may prioritise other expenses over energy, resulting in lower energy burdens than slightly wealthier yet fuel-poor households. The hypothetical nature of affordability considerations emerges,

emphasising the need to assess whether a high energy burden is requisite for adequate home comfort (Bouzarovski, 2014; Bouzarovski & Simcock, 2017).

Figure 6 - Energy burden on households' budget

The survey also reveals a significant distrust in the fairness of Greece's energy transition, with 35.9% expressing complete mistrust. This distrust highlights procedural justice concerns and underscores the importance of transparent processes and equitable decision-making to ensure the energy transition is perceived as fair and its benefits are universally felt.

Perceptions on Governance

The survey explored respondents' consensus on different energy transition approaches, employing a Likert scale for responses. The governance framework is critical in a just transition context. Investing in Renewable Energy (RE) installations allows consumers to become prosumers, actively producing some of their energy, thus reducing costs and potentially earning from surplus energy sales (Lowitzsch et al., 2020).

We aimed to understand attitudes towards various energy transition strategies and the roles of key stakeholders (figure 7). The survey evaluated how these strategies influenced local and regional development and provided insights for policymaking by measuring public

opinion. Over 60% supported Greek companies spearheading large-scale RE projects, whilst almost 20% strongly disagreed. Foreign companies' involvement saw greater resistance, with over half the respondents disapproving and only 15% in support. Public-private partnerships were viewed more favourably, with state-level partnerships backed by nearly 66% and municipal partnerships receiving slightly higher approval.

Cooperatives involving local entities and citizens in small-scale projects were particularly well-received, with over 65% support and 17.4% expressing complete agreement. While finally, partnerships between citizens and the public sector also received positive feedback from over two-thirds of participants.

Figure 7 - Level of agreement with types of RES investment partnerships

The survey unveiled varied views on energy transition methods. Public-private partnerships at state and local levels enjoyed more popularity than initiatives led solely by private companies. Local cooperatives were met with relatively high approval, contrasting with the scepticism towards foreign company involvement. The diversity in opinions emphasises the need for multiple transition strategies to reflect societal views.

Another finding highlighted a preference for the public sector to play a pivotal role in Greece's shift to renewables, with about 66.5% in support (figure 8). Moreover, nearly 31% advocated for a central role for local communities via partnerships. Enthusiasm for local cooperatives demonstrates support for distributive justice, signalling the value of empowering communities to achieve an equitable energy transition.

Figure 8 - Preferences on the primary governing stakeholder for RES deployment

Perceptions on participation

Participation is crucial for community-based initiatives, yet our findings indicate that a considerable number of respondents (39%) are unaware of local or state government sustainable energy projects. This points to the need for better communication and outreach to raise public awareness since only one-eighth of the respondents are both aware and knowledgeable about such government-led initiatives.

Views on the extent of citizen inclusion in energy transition decision-making vary (figure 9). A significant group (35.5%) feels completely excluded, while 19.4% perceive only minimal inclusion. Conversely, a quarter of respondents sense a moderate level of involvement, and 15.1% see substantial engagement. Notably, only a small fraction (5.1%) believes there is a high degree of citizen participation in energy transition decisions.

Figure 9 - Citizen's perceptions over citizens' engagement in RES decision making

Attitudes towards Energy Communities

The survey underscores a significant lack of awareness, familiarity and comprehension concerning ECs. Nearly 45% reported no knowledge of ECs, highlighting an urgent need to further information dissemination in Greece. About one-third had heard of ECs but lacked in-depth knowledge, while only 4.9% were well-informed, and 17.7% had moderate familiarity.

Figure 10 - Citizens level of awareness regarding energy communities

Despite this lack of knowledge, after a short presentation over the ECs definition and role tailored for the survey, a significant level of interest in participating in EC projects arises. Over half the respondents (54%) showed concrete interest in EC involvement after learning about their role, and a further 30% might consider participating with more information or motivation. Only 16% were uninterested. A statistical analysis over key variables influencing the willingness to participate in ECs revealed by no surprise that more affluent households have greater resources and access to information, which can also make their decision to participate in ECs initiatives easier. Thus, households' income levels are a key influencer on driving the interest of households to participate in an energy community. Specifically, those in the top income bracket (> 30,000 €) are 1.32 times more likely to be interested in joining an energy community. While consistently the higher the income group, the more likely is for a household to be interested in joining an energy community initiative (figure 11).

Educational attainment and energy literacy is also an important factor driving attitudes towards energy communities' participation. Prior knowledge over the institution and role of ECs significantly improves the willingness to participate in a project. Individuals with very good or adequate knowledge of ECs are 1.66 and 1.25 times more likely, respectively, to participate. Those with postgraduate degrees are 2.05 times more likely to possess such knowledge (Figure 12).

Figure 11 - Household's income influencing the willingness to participate in an EC

Figure 12 - Prior knowledge over EC influencing the willingness to participate in an EC

Observing the survey results so far, on the one hand there is an acknowledgement of the climate crisis emergency, accompanied with a public acceptance of RES while knowledge on ECs – as a way of actively involving communities to energy projects – is limited. The observed "social gap", where there is widespread support for renewable energy but a slower adoption of the renewable energy projects, is a matter that researchers have aimed to unravel (Eltham et al., 2008; Bell et al., 2013). The speculation is that this gap may be attributed to perceived

deficiencies in the fairness and quality of decision-making processes at the local level, influencing project outcomes (Huijts et al., 2012), just like what our findings indicate.

Acknowledging the importance of both extensive renewable energy projects implementation and social acceptance, scholars advocate for enhanced public engagement in planning processes. This is considered vital for fostering renewable development and ensuring a socially just transition in the energy landscape (Sovacool et al., 2016). Huijts et al. (2012) also emphasise the pivotal role of trust in shaping the acceptance of renewable energy projects. Marlin-Tackie et al. (2020) argued that public participation for promoting justice and fostering various positive socio-environmental outcomes, such as bolstering trust in government and industry. In this context, trust is identified as a key factor influencing perceptions of energy justice, as well as emotional responses that contribute to shaping attitudes toward both the energy projects itself as well as the involved actors (Dwyer & Bidwell, 2019). Promoting participation, transparency, and trust is vital for a socially just and environmentally sustainable energy transition.

Willingness-to-invest in Energy Communities

Taking a closer look to understand how ECs could contribute significantly to a fair energy transition in Greece, we've calculated responders' willingness to invest in these initiatives. To explore potential connections and determine whether a parametric analysis is appropriate, we employed Eta correlation, Spearman's rho correlation, and Kendall's Tau-b. After examining these correlations, it becomes evident that the willingness to invest shows very weak connections with the other variables. None of these correlations is significant enough to support a meaningful parametric analysis. Nevertheless, upon reviewing all the correlations, it can be suggested that education level, the income level and the percentage of income spent on energy bills may have a notable influence on the willingness to invest.

To gain insights into the appropriate amount to invest in an EC project, as indicated by the responses, we utilised a non-parametric analysis method. The analysis concluded that the willingness to invest is 1,723.88 euros per responder, which is a promising indicator of the potential for ECs to serve as a driving mechanism for a just energy transition in Greece. The fact that citizens are willing to financially commit to ECs suggests a high level of community engagement and interest in sustainable energy initiatives and reflects a commitment to collective action and community-driven solutions, aligning with the principles of participation and inclusivity within the energy justice framework. This is also evident in the rest of their responses since they recognize the potential positive effects of ECs on their communities, such as job creation, reduced energy costs, and enhanced energy security.

High willingness to invest could also send a strong signal to policymakers, as it indicates public support for renewable energy citizen initiatives. Policymakers should recognize these initiatives as a powerful tool for advancing the country's energy transition goals; fostering and

facilitating citizen participation in ECs should be a central policy objective, given that the public endorsement of such initiatives underscores the potential of the ECs framework to serve as a key proponent of advancing energy justice in Greece. In this context, given that a significant portion of respondents felt uninformed about local authorities and RES capabilities, there is a need for policy initiatives focused on education and awareness. Providing clear, accessible information about ECs, renewable energy benefits, and available investment opportunities can bridge this information gap.

Discussion

The survey results reveal a nuanced landscape of public perception and engagement with RES and ECs in Greece. While an evident public support for renewable energy emerges, with 73% of respondents expressing positive views, there is a stark contrast in the awareness and understanding of ECs. A significant majority, 44.7%, reported no knowledge of ECs, and 32.7% had limited knowledge despite encountering the term. This disparity highlights a critical gap between the endorsement of RES and the practical involvement in energy initiatives at the community level.

The lack of awareness about ECs could be attributed to insufficient dissemination of information, which suggests that educational and outreach efforts need to be strengthened. The finding that households with higher income levels and greater educational attainment show more interest in participating in ECs underscores the need for inclusive strategies that ensure all community members have equal opportunities to engage. This is particularly important since ECs are instrumental in localising the energy transition, fostering community resilience, and enabling democratic participation in energy decisions.

The data indicates that nearly half of the surveyed households allocate a significant portion of their income to energy expenses, with 12% spending more than 10% of their annual income. This highlights the pressing issue of energy poverty and the need for ECs to provide affordable energy solutions. The willingness of households in the highest income quintile to participate in ECs, being 1.32 times more likely than others, reflects the existing socioeconomic divide that may hinder the broader adoption of ECs. A just transition must consider these disparities, ensuring that the benefits of the energy transition are equitably shared and not limited to the more affluent citizens.

Educational attainment and energy literacy were found to be important drivers of attitudes towards EC participation. Those with very good knowledge of ECs were 1.66 times more likely to participate, and those with adequate knowledge were 1.25 times more likely. This suggests that increasing public knowledge and understanding of ECs could significantly increase participation rates. Policies and initiatives must, therefore, prioritise energy literacy and education to increase the public's willingness to engage in the energy transition.

The data also reveals a social gap, where a significant portion of respondents (39%) are unaware of sustainable energy initiatives by local or state governments, indicating a disconnect between policy actions and public awareness. This suggests a need for enhanced communication and transparency in government-led sustainable energy programs. Moreover, the perception of citizen involvement in energy decision-making varies, with 35.5% perceiving no involvement and only 5.1% feeling very much involved. This points to a perceived deficit in public engagement, which could be addressed by fostering a participatory culture in energy governance.

Considering these results, and the willingness of the surveyed households to potentially participate (with 54% of respondents showing a concrete interest and 30% being potentially receptive) and invest significant resources in ECs, their role in the just energy transition becomes even more pivotal. ECs have the potential to bridge the gap between public support for RES and actual involvement in sustainable energy practices. They can act as platforms for education, engagement, and empowerment, democratising the energy transition and fostering a sense of ownership among community members.

However, the success of ECs in facilitating a just transition is contingent on addressing the barriers identified in the survey. Overcoming the knowledge gap, mitigating the effects of socioeconomic disparities, and enhancing public participation in energy decisions are critical steps. Policymakers and stakeholders must collaborate to design strategies that are inclusive, educational, and transparent, ensuring that the transition to a sustainable energy future is equitable and just for all members of society.

In conclusion, the survey provides valuable insights into the public's perception and readiness to engage in ECs as a means to achieve energy justice and a just transition in Greece. The findings underscore the importance of addressing information asymmetries, socioeconomic factors, and participatory mechanisms to facilitate a truly inclusive and democratic energy transition. As Greece moves towards a sustainable low-emission future, ECs stand out as a catalyst for change, provided they are accessible and approachable for citizens from all walks of life.

Conclusion

This paper provided a comprehensive understanding of the role of ECs and their contribution to achieving energy justice and facilitating a just energy transition in Greece. Through a comprehensive survey of Greek households, we have gathered insights into public perceptions of the energy transition, awareness and attitudes towards ECs, and the willingness to participate in and invest in ECs. The survey has revealed several critical findings:

- There is a significant lack of awareness and understanding of ECs among the general population, despite a strong public support for renewable energy sources. This indicates a need for targeted information and education campaigns to bridge this

knowledge gap and encourage community participation in ECs. Nevertheless, we reveal a promising inclination among respondents to actually invest in ECs.

- Energy poverty remains a major concern in Greece, with a large portion of households dedicating a significant share of their income to energy costs. This underscores the urgency of integrating energy justice considerations into policy measures to ensure affordable and equitable access to energy for all.
- Socioeconomic disparities influence interest and participation in ECs, with higher-income households being more likely to engage. This highlights the need for policies that promote inclusivity and ensure that the benefits of ECs and the broader energy transition are accessible to diverse socioeconomic groups.
- Public trust in the equity and inclusiveness of the energy transition process is low, emphasising the need for improved communication, transparency, and participatory mechanisms in energy governance.

Based on these findings, we can provide several policy recommendations to strengthen the role of ECs in achieving a just energy transition in Greece. Firstly, the implementation of comprehensive information campaigns and educational programs aiming to raise public awareness about the benefits and functioning of ECs. This should involve accessible, community-driven initiatives that demystify ECs and showcase successful case studies. Then the development of targeted support mechanisms is needed for low-income households to participate in ECs, such as subsidies, low-interest loans, or grants. These measures should aim to alleviate energy poverty and ensure that the transition to renewable energy does not exacerbate existing inequalities. This should also be followed by the encouragement of the establishment of ECs with diverse membership, including representation from various income levels and social groups. To do so incentives can be created for ECs that demonstrate high levels of inclusivity and equity in their membership and governance structures. When it comes to public participation in energy transition, EC should be involved in decision-making in planning and development processes. This could include participatory budgeting for local energy projects, community consultation forums, and transparent reporting on energy policy outcomes. Finally, monitoring and evaluating the impact of ECs on local development and social cohesion is essential. Data collection and analysis should be ongoing to assess the effectiveness of ECs in promoting energy justice and informing the refinement of policies and programs.

In conclusion, ECs present a unique opportunity to democratise the energy system in Greece, foster social and environmental justice, and contribute to the fight against climate change. However, realising the full potential of ECs requires concerted effort from policymakers, industry stakeholders, and communities themselves to ensure that the transition is not only technologically and economically viable but also socially equitable and inclusive. At the moment this is not scaled enough though with recognition and adequate support, citizens' led

energy initiatives such as ECs can be a powerful tool for advancing the country's just energy transition goals.

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Conflict of interest

All authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest and did not receive financial compensation for this project. The views expressed in this paper are purely those of the authors and may not in any circumstances be regarded as stating an official position of the European Commission.

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